

CHALLENGES IN TEACHING SPEAKING TO YOUNG LEARNERS BY ROLE-PLAY ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The students often find some problems in practising English speaking. The problem frequently found is that their native language causes them difficult to use the foreign language. Other reason is because of motivation lack to practice the second language in daily conversation. They are also too shy and afraid to take part in the conversation. Many factors can cause the problem of the students' speaking skills namely the students' interest, the material, and the media among others including the technique in teaching English. There are many ways that can be done by the students to develop their ability in speaking English. The appropriate technique used by the English teacher also supports their interested in practising their speaking. One of the techniques that can be applied is role play.

Keywords: Teaching Speaking, method, technology, role-play activity.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is perhaps the most fundamental of human skills, and because we do it constantly, we do not often stop to examine the processes involved. The students often find some problems in practising English speaking. The problem frequently found is that their native language causes them difficult to use the foreign language. Other reason is because of motivation lack to practice the second language in daily conversation. They are also too shy and afraid to take part in the conversation. Many factors can cause the problem of the students' speaking skills namely the students' interest, the material, and the media among others including the technique in teaching

English. There are many ways that can be done by the students to develop their ability in speaking English. The appropriate method used by the English teacher also supports their interested in practising their speaking [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One of the techniques that can be used by the English teacher is Role – Play activity. Role play is very important in teaching speaking because it gives students an opportunity to practice communicating in different social contexts and in different social roles. In addition, it also allows students to be creative and to put themselves in another person is placed for a while.

According to Stephen D. Hattings based on his observation in the conversation class, the role play would seem to be the ideal activity in which students could use their English creatively and it aims to stimulate a conversation situation in which students might find them-selves and give them an opportunity to practice and develop their communication skill.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When teaching young learners, we constantly have to keep in mind the fact that what we have in front of us is a mixed class with varied abilities, expectations, motivation level, knowledge and last but not least, different learning styles. Thus, we need to vary our approaches and offer as much opportunity as possible to make the whole class find a little something to hold on to, expand and grow.

Young learners are like sponges, they soak up everything we say and how we say it. Thus clear and correct pronunciation is of vital importance, since young learners repeat exactly what they hear. What has been learned at an early stage is difficult to change later on. One rule that applied here is slowly and steadily through constant revision and recycling. With the help of mixed activities, such as dialogues, choral revision, chants, songs, poems and rhymes, students speaking abilities grow, their pronunciation gets better and their awareness of the language improves. When applying the above- mentioned tools into the teaching practice, what should be kept

in mind is that interaction is an important way of learning. Therefore, increased oral emphasis should be included in our teaching to give the students as much speaking time as possible.

Role-play is any speaking activity when you either put yourself into somebody else's shoes, or when you stay in your own shoes but put yourself into an imaginary situation!

Imaginary people – The joy of role-play is that students can 'become' anyone they like for a short time! The President, the Queen, a millionaire, a pop star the choice is endless! Students can also take on the opinions of someone else. 'For and Against' debates can be used and the class can be split into those who are expressing views in favour and those who are against the theme.

Imaginary situations – Functional language for a multitude of scenarios can be activated and practiced through role-play. 'At the restaurant', 'Checking in at the airport', 'Looking for lost property' are all possible [3].

Role defined as the person whom an actor represents in a film or play, while role play is a method of acting out particular ways of behaving or pretending to be other people who deal with new situations. It is used in training courses language learning and psychotherapy.

In this case, Gillian Porter Ladousse illustrated that when students assume a Role-play, they play a part (either their own or somebody else) in specific situation. Play means that is taken on in a safe environment in which students are as an inventive and playful as possible.

According to Crookal, there is a little consensus on the terms used in the role playing and simulation literature. A few of the terms that often used interchangeably are, simulation, games, role play, simulation-game, role play simulation, and role playing game.

There seem to be some agreement; however, simulation is a broader concept than role playing. Simulations are complex lengthy and relatively inflexible events.

Role play, on the other hand, can be a quite simple and brief technique to organize. It is also highly flexible, leaving much more scope for the exercise of individual variation, initiative and imagination. And role play also included in simulation as well.

In view of the persons taking an actor, Gillian explained that there are several types of role. The first is the roles which correspond to a real need in the students' lives. In this category, it involves such roles as doctors dealing with patients, or salesman traveling abroad.

The second type of role is the students play themselves in a variety of situations which may or may not have direct experience. The example which include in this category is a customer complaining or a passenger asking for information. The third type is the type that few students will ever experience directly themselves, but it is easy to play because the teachers have such vast indirect experience of them. The television journalist is a good example of this type and it is very useful kind of role taken from real life. The last type is fantasy roles, which are fictitious, imaginary, and possible even absurd.

In case of role play activities, according to Donn Byrne, role play can be grouped into two forms, scripted and unscripted role play. In details, those types of role play activities described as follows [1].

This type involves interpreting either the textbook dialogue or reading text in the form of speech. The main function of the text after all is to convey the meaning of language items in a memorably way.

For more details, an example of scripted role plays dialogue and reading text and how the process is:

Man : Good morning,sir ! Director : Good morning.

Man : I am coming to ask you for a job,sir !

Director : Take a seat,please !

Man : Thank you sir, is there any vacancy for me, sir ? I am unemployed right now.

Director : What is your education background ?

Man : I have graduated from STAIN Pamekasan in Economic Faculty for accounting Major. So I am competent in accounting.

Director : Have you ever been experienced before being an accountant ?

Man : I Have sir, i have enough experienced for administration staff at a small company.

Director : How many years ? Man : More than two years.

Director : Ok. Congratulation!! I am looking for an energetic and healthy young man that used to work hard. Welcome at my company as administration staff here.

Man: Thank you, sir.

To demonstrate a role play activity based on the dialogue, the procedures given by Adrian Doff is as follows: First, the teacher guides the role play by writing these prompts: (where? / air mail / how much? / post box? / thanks). Talk as you write to show what the prompts mean. If necessary, go through the prompts one by one, and get students to give sentences or question for each one. Call two students to the front: one play the role as Angela and the other one is the post office clerk. They should improvise the conversation using the prompts to help them. Point out that the conversation should be similar to the one in the textbook, but not exactly the same; the conversation can be shorter than the presentation dialogue. It should just cover the main points indicated by the prompts. Call out a few other pairs of students in turn, and ask them to have other conversation based on the prompts.

Based on these procedures, the writer views that the ways of organizing this dialogue can be carried out into pairs of students who would improvise a conversation in front of class, in turns. The teacher can also ask the students to

practice the conversation privately with their partners before they act it out in front of the class.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, role play is a technique which can develop students' fluency in target language, promotes students to speak or interact with others in the classroom, increases motivation and makes the teaching and learning process more enjoyable.

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